

ON THE EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE COMPLETE COMPLIANCE
MATRIX OF GLASS- AND CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC LAMINATES
DEPENDENT ON TEMPERATURE

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Summary

The increasing application of GFRP and CFRP materials in geometrically complicated structural elements requires an improved knowledge of the various physical material properties. Fibre-reinforced plastics are anisotropic materials, whose physical material properties depend on structure and orientation.

The present study determines, on an experimental basis, all 12 coefficients of elasticity S_{ik} of 9 different types of composite materials. 5 GFRPs and 4 CFRPs are tested. These materials are commonly used fibrous composites.

Depending on the fibre orientation, the materials are orthotropic or transversely isotropic respectively. In particular, the temperature dependence of all coefficients of elasticity S_{ik} of glass fibre-reinforced unsaturated polyester resins (GFR-UP) is tested within the temperature range from 20°C - 70°C.

Introduction

Previous studies have been predominantly concerned with determining only the coefficients of elasticity S_{ik} in the planes of the laminates in fibre-reinforced plastics. The coefficients of elasticity normal to the plane of the laminate—less important from a technological point of view—were estimated, if required.

The knowledge of the coefficients of elasticity S_{ik} of the anisotropic material is a prerequisite for the exact calculation of the stress-strain behaviour of load-bearing structures (panels, plates, shells etc.) in particular concerning special sections around defects and holes.

Depending on the degree of anisotropy there are 9, 6 or 5 different coefficients of elasticity S_{ik} .

The Stress-Strain Behaviour of Elastic Anisotropic Space Structures

In order to illustrate the stress-strain relations in elastic space structures under mechanical load, an infinite prismatic volume element can be regarded as a continuum.

Under mechanical stress 3 normal stress components σ_i and 6 shearing stress components τ_{ik} (where $i, k = 1, 2, 3$ and x, y, z respectively) can be determined, see Fig. 1. In this connection each of the 9 stress components can produce 9 strain components, i.e. there are a resulting 81 coefficients of elasticity. However, due to the conditions of symmetry and equilibrium, the number of numerically different coefficients of elasticity can be reduced substantially, see Voigt (1), Hörig (2) and Jones (3).

In the case of orthotropy with loading in the direction of the principal axes, the following law of elasticity can be established:

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_x &= S_{11} \cdot \sigma_x + S_{12} \cdot \sigma_y + S_{13} \cdot \sigma_z \\ \epsilon_y &= S_{21} \cdot \sigma_x + S_{22} \cdot \sigma_y + S_{23} \cdot \sigma_z \\ \epsilon_z &= S_{31} \cdot \sigma_x + S_{32} \cdot \sigma_y + S_{33} \cdot \sigma_z \\ \gamma_{yz} &= S_{44} \cdot \tau_{yz} \\ \gamma_{zx} &= S_{55} \cdot \tau_{zx} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= S_{66} \cdot \tau_{xy}\end{aligned}$$

with 9 independent elastic constants, where

$$S_{ik} = S_{ki}$$

The first index denotes the direction of strain, the second index the direction of stress that causes the strain; and the following correlation of numbers and coordinates applies:

$$1 - x; 2 - y; 3 - z$$

In the notation commonly used in engineering we thus have:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{1}{E_x} \cdot \sigma_x + \frac{-\nu_{xy}}{E_y} \cdot \sigma_y + \frac{-\nu_{xz}}{E_z} \cdot \sigma_z$$

$$\epsilon_y = \frac{-\nu_{yx}}{E_x} \cdot \sigma_x + \frac{1}{E_y} \cdot \sigma_y + \frac{-\nu_{yz}}{E_z} \cdot \sigma_z$$

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{-\nu_{zx}}{E_x} \cdot \sigma_x + \frac{-\nu_{zy}}{E_y} \cdot \sigma_y + \frac{1}{E_z} \cdot \sigma_z$$

$$\gamma_{yz} = \frac{1}{G_{yz}} \cdot \tau_{yz}$$

$$\gamma_{zx} = \frac{1}{G_{zx}} \cdot \tau_{zx}$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = \frac{1}{G_{xy}} \cdot \tau_{xy}$$

The indicated relations form the basis of calculation of the stress-strain behaviour of cross-ply laminates, or, respectively, of individual unidirectionally reinforced laminate in an arbitrarily constructed multi-ply composite; in the latter case, however, the stresses normal to the plane of the laminate are neglected.

The Influence of Temperature

Like all space structures, three-dimensional composite materials, too, are liable to alter their geometry due to a change in temperature. Compared to steel or reinforcement fibres made of glass or carbon, plastics have a high coefficient of thermal expansion α_{θ} . Carbon fibres, on the other hand, are characterized by a negative coefficient of thermal expansion, i.e. contrary to other materials they contract in rising temperatures.

In the case of composites, the coefficients of thermal expansion α_{θ} of GFRPs and CFRPs are dependent not only on the properties of the individual components (fibre, resin) their volume content and orientation, but also on geometrical circumstances (dimensions of test specimens) and manufacturing conditions (adhesion, possible inclusion of air, etc). In parti-

cular, direction- and geometry-dependent obstructions to deformation have to be taken into account due to the different values of E , ν and α_0 of fibres and matrices under elevated temperature. For further information, see Scharr (4). Furthermore, it is to be expected that the coefficients of elasticity themselves are temperature-dependent.

Methods for the Experimental Determination of the Coefficients of Elasticity

The characteristic data of elasticity for the computation of the stress strain behaviour of composites can be determined by way of static and dynamic tests. Static tests are those in which test specimens are loaded quasistatically, e.g. in tensile tests, compression tests or bending tests designed to determine the moduli of elasticity the coefficients of transversal strain and shear moduli.

In the dynamic tests for determining the coefficients of elasticity, the internal vibration and the damping behaviour of the material are measured and analysed, e.g. in the torsion vibration test for determining the shear moduli.

In order to determine the coefficients of elasticity analysed in this study, static tests were employed:

- the tensile testing machine for determining the S_{ii} or the moduli of elasticity respectively, according to Neuhaus (5)
- the torsion testing machine for determining the other S_{ik} or the shear moduli respectively, according to Neuhaus (5) and Krabbe (6)

These were tests with low loading and all readings were taken rapidly, in order not to violate the premises of the theory of elasticity.

In addition, the machines were provided with air-conditioning chambers which made measurements below the glass transition temperature for UP-resin of 145°C and in the range from 20°C - 70°C possible. The measurements were performed on identical 240 mm long prismatic rods that were directly cut out of the GFRP-panels (measuring 450 x 450 mm, and 11-16 mm in thickness) and the CFRP-panels (measuring 380 x 380 x 8 mm) respectively, along the principal axes; or they were constructed by sticking together individual cubes that were taken from along the third principal axis z , i.e. the axis normal to the plane of reinforcement xy , see Fig. 2.

The adhesive used in this latter case is the same type of resin employed in the various test materials.

The readings obtained were analysed according to the $R(p)$ -method described by Hörig (2), which had been used earlier by Neuhaus (5) and Krabbe (6) for the investigation of the anisotropy of wood.

Materials Analysed

CFRPs

5 glass fibre-reinforced unsaturated polyester resin (GFR-UP) panels were manufactured for the tests.

A heat resistant UP-resin (Leguval W 25) with a wide area of application was used as matrix.

Glass filament mats as well as bidirectional or unidirectional woven glass filament fabrics, see Table 1, served as reinforcements. Due to the various possibilities of placing and arranging these fibrous reinforcements, one mat laminate, two woven fabric laminates, and two mixed laminates could be produced.

Table 1: GFRP - Test Materials

Composite Material		Reinforcement Ply Weight	Fibre Content Vol.-o/o
Laminate 1	XXXXXX	Glass Filament	
Mat Laminate	XXXXXX	Mat	23
	XXXXXX	M 123-50	
	XXXXXX	450 g/m ²	
Laminate 2	+++++	Woven Glass	Glass Filament
Mixed	XXXXXX	Filament	Mat
Laminate	+++++	Fabric (BD)	M 123-50
	XXXXXX	92140	450 g/m ²
	+++++	390 g/m ²	
Laminate 3	+++++	Woven Glass	Glass Filament
Mixed	XXXXXX	Filament	Mat
Laminate	+++++	Fabric (UD)	M 123-50
	XXXXXX	92145	450 g/m ²
	+++++	220 g/m ²	
Laminate 4	+++++	Woven Glass	
Woven Cloth	+++++	Filament	
Laminate	+++++	Fabric (BD)	30
	+++++	92140	
	+++++	390 g/m ²	
Laminate 5	+++++	Woven Glass	
Woven Cloth	+++++	Filament	
Laminate	+++++	Fabric (UD)	41
	+++++	92146	
	+++++	425 g/m ²	
xxxxx Glass Filament Mat ++++ Woven Glass Filament Fabric (BD) +++++ Woven Glass Filament Fabric (UD)			

CFRPs

The structure of the CFR-plastics can be inferred from Table 2.

Composite Material	Prepreg-System Curing Temperature	CF: Type Fibre Content (Vol. o/o)	Prepreg Layers Arrangement	
CFRP-1 786	Fibredux 914 C-T300 UD-Prepreg 180°C	HT-Fibres*) 60 o/o	64 0°	↑↓
CFRP-2 813	Hexcel F 550 UD-Prepreg 120°C	HT-Fibres 60 o/o	32 0°	↑↓
CFRP-3 787	Fibredux 914 C-T300 180°C	HT-Fibres 60 o/o	64 0° / 90°	↑↓ ↔
CFRP-4 812	Hexcel F 550 UD-Prepreg 120°C	HT-Fibres 60 o/o	32 0° / 90°	↑↓ ↔

*) HT high tensile strength

Test Results

The test results are shown in Fig. 3 - 8. The moduli of elasticity and the degree of their temperature-dependence are given in Fig. 3 for GFRPs and in Fig. 6 and 7 for CFRPs. It becomes apparent that the greatest temperature-dependence occurs perpendicular to the plane of the laminate xy. The influence of temperature is reduced with increasing fibre content.

Fig. 4 shows the influence of temperature on the Poisson's ratios of GFRPs. The influence of temperature is lowered as the fibre content increases.

The influence of temperature on the shear moduli is shown in Fig. 5 for GFRPs and in Fig. 6 and 8 for CFRPs. With an increase in temperature from 20°C to 70°C they may be reduced up to 50 o/o.

The elastic moduli and the shear moduli perpendicular to the reinforcement layers can be as much as 50 - 200 o/o higher than the corresponding elastic coefficients of the resin matrix, depending on the fibre content. In practice, however, the calculations often are incorrectly done with the relatively small elastic values of the matrix.

Figure 1 - Stresses on a volume element where x, y, z are the cristallographic principle axes.

Figure 2 - Manufacture of the test specimens.

Figure 3 - Moduli of Elasticity E_x, E_y, E_z of GFRP.

Figure 4 - Poisson's Ratios $\nu_{xy}, \nu_{xz}, \nu_{yz}, \nu_{yx}, \nu_{zx}, \nu_{zy}$ of GFRP.

Figure 5 - Shear Moduli G_{xy}, G_{yz}, G_{zx} of GFRP.

Figure 6 - Moduli of Elasticity E and Shear Moduli G of CFRP (Temperature $\vartheta=20^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 7 - Moduli of Elasticity E_x, E_y, E_z of CFRP.

Figure 8 - Shear Modulus G_{xy} of CFRP.

Conclusions

This study presents a first attempt to determine the complete compliance matrix of GFRPs and CFRPs in identical specimens.

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